

Experimental testing of fiber-coupled miniature organic fast neutron scintillation detectors in nuclear research reactors from 1 W to 1 kW

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ABSTRACT

This work presents the experimental characterization of sub-mm³ fiber-coupled fast neutron detectors based on organic scintillators, performed in both the zero-power reactor CROCUS and the BME Training Reactor. These detectors are of interest due to their ability to perform sub-mm scale measurements. These sub-mm live measurements can provide kW neutron measurement datasets for multiphysics code validation toward Nuclear Power Plant (NPP) vessel fluence calculation. The herein used detector system has hitherto not been tested with powers above 100 W, so experiments were conducted to assess its stability and performance under higher power conditions. The study focuses on powers up to 1 kW and a flux of 10^{10} n·cm⁻²·s⁻¹ in BME and compares the results with reference measurements from the CROCUS reactor at low power. Pulse Shape Discrimination (PSD) enables fast neutron counting as a function of the reactor power, and linear fittings were established for both reactor datasets to assess their sensitivity, consistency, and scalability of response. Measurements show a non-linear counting response of the detectors above 300 W, likely caused by pileups. At a power of 1 kW, during tens of seconds we observe a decrease in the count rate over time, likely caused by degradation of the scintillator or the fiber. Future work includes investigations on the pulse waveforms at 3,5 and 10 kW to better understand the phenomena of non-linearity and detector deterioration. These results provide first insights into the operational limits of the developed detectors and guide future optimization for applications of fiber-coupled scintillation experiments in higher-power reactor environments.

Keywords: Miniature detectors, fiber-coupled, reactor physics, fast neutron detection, research reactors

1. INTRODUCTION

The operational lifetime of Nuclear Power Plants (NPP) is primarily limited by the neutron irradiation (fluence) accumulated in the reactor pressure vessel (RPV). To date, simulation codes are used to compute the RPV fluence. These calculation schemes carry significant uncertainties and regulators therefore determine conservative safety margins with respect to the radiation-induced embrittlement and thus reduced fracture toughness of the RPV.

To potentially reduce the margins and increase the operational lifetimes of NPP, it was proposed to propagate 'high-fidelity' information from within the reactor core, such as thermal effects or the local neutron distribution with a sub-pin resolution. The EVEREST project (Experiments for Validation and Enhancement of the RE-actor preSSure vessel fluence assessmentT) is a Euratom research consortium that aims to develop multiphysics codes with a sub-cm scale resolution. These codes are to be validated against experimental data provided by three research reactors within the project, including

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the BME training reactor in Budapest. These reactors are specifically chosen due to the appearance of multiphysics effects between 1 kW and 10 kW [1], [2], [3], [4] used for the multiphysics code validation.

Miniature thermal neutron detectors have already been successfully developed e.g. at EPFL [5], [6]. However, they are not suited for high power research reactors (strong flux and temperature peaks around 50 °C) due to saturation. For EVEREST, particular attention is given to fast neutron detection because of their significant contribution to the vessel fluence.

Currently few datasets in neutron detection provide live, sub-centimeter-scale measurements, particularly for fast neutrons. Such detectors have been developed but their price and export control is a barrier to their use [7]. Miniature organic scintillators are well suited for this purpose, offering fast neutron detection along low sensitivity for high power measurements. This paper presents the testing of our miniature organic fast neutron scintillation detector under high fluxes environments (up to $10^{10} \text{ n}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$). Previously tested and characterized at EPFL, the core of this paper is the characterization in higher neutron fluxes in the BME training reactor. Results in both reactors will be compared.

2. SETUP: EXPERIMENTAL FACILITIES AND NEUTRON DETECTOR

2.1. The CROCUS Zero Power reactor

CROCUS is a partially submerged light-water moderated and uranium-fueled reactor located at EPFL in Switzerland [8]. Its nominal power of 100 W corresponds to a total flux of $\sim 2.5 \cdot 10^9 \text{ cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ with a thermal to fast ratio of 0.5 in the core center [9], [10], [11]. It operates at atmospheric pressure and ambient temperature. The water temperature is controlled around 20 °C. The reactor core is organized in two zones (see Fig.1): an inner squared lattice of 336-1.806 wt% enriched UO_2 fuel rods with a pitch of 1.837 cm and an outer squared lattice of 180 metallic uranium rods (in the current configuration [9], [6]) enriched at 0.947 wt% with a pitch of 2.917 cm. The reactor is mainly operated using the water level through a spillway with an accuracy of $\pm 0.1 \text{ mm}$ (up to 0.4 pcm).

Figure 1. Overview of CROCUS zero power reactor. Schematic isometric view on the left and top view with the core configuration on the right.

The neutron population is monitored using two Photonis CFUM21 10-mg ^{235}U fission chambers (East and West), used in pulse mode as calibrated power monitors over the entire operation range.

2.2. Budapesti Műszaki és Gazdaságtudományi Egyetem (BME) training reactor

The BME training reactor is an open pool-type reactor based in Budapest, Hungary. This reactor has a nominal power of 100 kW, equivalent to $\sim 2.7 \cdot 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ total neutron flux at core center. It is moderated and cooled by demineralized light water and has a graphite reflector. The reactor vessel is composed of a 10 mm thick aluminum wall with a height of 6 m and a diameter of 1.4 m (see Fig.2). The

reactor can operate either in forced circulation or under natural convection. For the experiments further developed in this paper, the reactor was in natural circulation configuration.

Figure 2. Overview of the BME training reactor. Vertical cut of reactor. In yellow the core barrel, in green the aluminum vessel, in red the irradiation channels and in blue is the concrete [12](a), Core configuration [12].

The reactor core is composed of 24 EK-10 type fuel assemblies, 41 graphite reflector blocks and 7 water irradiation position that form a 8×9 lattice (see Fig.2). It is equipped with 4 absorber rods: 2 safety rods (between E6 and F5 and between D5 and E4) and 2 control rods (AUT between C4 and D3 and MAN between C6 and D5). These rods are inserted from the top of the core in between the assemblies. They are operated directly by an operator, or automatically with a central control unit adjusting the AUT control rod.

The training reactor is housing five neutron detector in the air-filled channels around the core. Two CFUL08 fission chambers are used in pulse mode and three KNK-53M boron-lined, gamma compensated ionization chambers operated in current mode. The following experiments used the recorded signal of one of these three boron-lined detector. The recording detector is placed 140 mm left and 35 mm above the A1 position on Figure 2. For the experiments, aluminum hand positioning rods of about 7 m were used with plastic tubes at their extremities, hosting our detectors. These allowed detector insertion in the inter-assemblies channels, used as irradiation slots.

2.3. Miniature Organic Scintillation System (MOSS)

The MOSS detectors are developed at EPFL [13] for high resolution neutron detection. They are composed of three main parts: the scintillator for fast neutron detection, the optical fiber as a signal carrier, and a Photomultiplier Tube (PMT). In these experiments, the scintillator used is the Eljen EJ-276D [14]. The scintillators are manually cut from an industrial size bloc ($5 \cdot 5 \cdot 5$ mm) to sizes that are sub- 0.5 mm³.

Multiple sizes were obtained, from 0.35 mm³ to 0.08 mm³ to have different sensitivity aiming for high fluxes operations. These sizes also enable to put them in space-reduced environments. The scintillator is coupled to a 20 m Mitsubishi Super-ESKA PMMA optical fiber [15], [16] ($\varnothing 2.1$ mm total and $\varnothing 1.0$ mm core) via the Eljen EJ-550 optical silicone grease (see Fig.3). The junction is protected by an aluminum cap ($\varnothing 2.1$ mm). On the other side of the fiber is a Photo Multiplier Tube (PMT) for scintillation light detection. Two PMT types are used in this paper: two H3178-51 model (from now on H3) and one H12690-00-01 (from now on H1) model from Hamamatsu, the main difference being the size of the scintillator, the light sensitivity and the gain (higher for H1). A special fiber coupling cap is used for the coupling along EJ-550 optical grease (see Fig.3). The output signal of the PMTs is analyzed using a

CAEN DT5730S digitizer [17] with DPP-PSD firmware [18](see Fig.3).

The scintillator is sensitive to both neutrons and gamma-rays. To perform neutron detection, we are doing Pulse Shape Discrimination using the pulse gradient analysis method [19]. Previous developments have shown the development and working of these detectors with different sources such as Pu-Be, or the CROCUS reactor [13].

Figure 3. Overview of the three main part of the MOSS: Scintillator coupled on the fiber with EJ-550 optical grease (a), PMT assembly with its fiber coupling cap (b), plus the acquisition system (c)

3. IRRADIATION TESTING

This section is dedicated to the fast neutron detection experiments performed both in CROCUS and BME training reactor. The first tests in CROCUS are providing the detector reference values, whereas BME irradiation test its capabilities at the targeted higher fluence rate levels.

3.1. Detector characterization: from 1 W to 100 W in CROCUS

This sub-section aims to characterize the MOSS detector in CROCUS. The maximum used reactor power is 90 W, i.e. about $10^9 \text{cm}^{-2} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ in fast flux, without thermal feedback as is expected for such a facility and power level. These conditions are adequate for 'clean' measurements with multiple MOSS detector versions. All experiments conducted in CROCUS consisted of irradiation at several power levels with the detector placed in the empty guide tube of the southeast control rod. The detector is placed axially at mid-height of the core, i.e. about 50 cm from the fuel bottom. From now on the scintillator size on the detector will be denoted as 'MOSS-size'. We expected to observe PSD plots that exhibit a clearly distinguishable neutron region separated from the gamma-ray noise and pileups. Moreover, we expected the MOSS count rate to be linearly dependent on the reactor power or neutron flux up to the maximum power.

The PSD method consists of separating neutron and gamma-ray pulses by using their difference in luminescence decay time using a Tail Over Total integral ratio (ToT, see [13]). We thereby obtain a 2D-histogram that allows the selection of a Region Of Interest (ROI) for fast neutron detection [20], [19]. Figure 4 (a) shows the PSD histogram for a 90 W irradiation in CROCUS with a MOSS-0.3 mm³. We observe a clear cluster in the ToT region of 0.04-0.4, defining our ROI (in red) for fast neutron detection. The 1000 charges deposited threshold was chosen in order to be conservative regarding gamma-ray events observed to spill into said ROI region. The ROI provides the live fast neutron counting as shown in Figure 4 [13]. The blue/green region in low deposited energy correspond to pile-ups effects and gamma-ray signal. Due to the size reduction of the scintillator, the gamma-ray signal is reduced to the lower energy band.

Figure 4 (b) shows the comparison between the MOSS-0.3mm³ and the reactor monitor #2 of CROCUS. In this case we used an optimized ROI. The counting mean is following the reference within one sigma along the different power steps. This also demonstrates the proportionality of the detector response up to 90 W. MOSS also follows the fast power drop at the end of the experiment. However, as we can see, a very small increase in the residual shows a negligible discrepancy between both detectors at this step of the development.

Figure 4. MOSS-0.3 mm³ Pulse Shape Discrimination plot (a): in blue the gamma-ray signal, noise and pileup events, in red the ROI for fast neutron detection. (b): MOSS-0.3 mm³ compared to the reference detector (CFUM21 power monitor) during a power steps experiment. The corresponding axes are the same color as the data points, i.e., blue for the MOSS count rate and red for the reactor power.

The MOSS-0.3 mm³ detector demonstrated good repeatability, as confirmed by several power step experiments that exhibited consistent response patterns.

3.2. Test irradiations: from 100 W to 1 kW in the BME training reactor

We next present experiments at higher powers in the BME training reactor. Multiple MOSSs detectors equipped with different sizes of EJ-276D scintillators, as well as different scintillator types (e.g., Stilbene, not discussed in this paper) were tested. Repetitions were performed with the two smallest ones: MOSS-0.24 mm³ and MOSS-0.15 mm³. Thanks to their small volume, the amount of gamma-ray interaction and pileups is reduced, enhancing relative neutron counting efficiency [21]. For these measurements, the pulse detection thresholds were increased relative to those used in CROCUS—from 61 mV to 110 mV for H1 and from 37 mV to 73 mV for H3—in order to minimize the low-energy noise band. By doing it, we decrease the overall signal recorded by the digitizer and thus reducing dead time. The optimal threshold values were determined by adjusting the threshold level at low reactor power (around 10 W) until the noisy low-energy component disappeared from the PSD plot. For all experiments, MOSSs were placed in the top left water channel of the E6 assembly (red dot on Figure 2). The detectors were axially set at middle core — 30 cm above the core bottom — in the plastic channels described in Part.2.2.

Figure 5. Evolution of PSD histograms of MOSS-0.15 mm³ as a function of the power steps in the BME training reactor for the MOSS-0.15mm³ equipped with H3 PMT.

Figure 5 shows the PSD plot for different power levels. The principal features are similar to the PSD plots obtained in CROCUS, though we observe significant added signals with increasing power. Over time, the high density cluster (in yellow) at low energies is shifting up in ToT. This behavior, along with

the onset of Cerenkov radiation at approximately 300 W, reflects an increase of interaction rates in the scintillator and fiber, and thus the increased occurrence of pileups.

Above 300 W, Figure 5 and Figure 6 show a growing of the neutron cluster and divergence of count rate compared to the reference monitor respectively. The enlargement on the x-axis of the neutron cluster along the divergence of the signals shows that gamma-rays are mischaracterized as neutron. Multiple gamma-ray signals are recorded simultaneously resulting in a ToT around the neutron one and high energy amplitude leading the detection signal in the ROI. Despite the threshold set for the ROI to exclude potential gamma-rays/noises, the high interaction rate does not allow to discriminate the sum-peaks.

The result of the ROI integration is show in Figure 6 for both MOSS-0.15 mm³ and MOSS-0.24 mm³. MOSS-0.15 mm³ follows the reference within one sigma up to 300 W whereas MOSS-0.24 mm³ only within 2 sigma with a clear trend. At higher powers, we observe a count rate decrease for both MOSSs where it should remain stable. These observations suggest an immediate degradation of the detector system, the cause of which is still under investigation. Testable hypotheses for future work include optical fiber darkening or scintillator degradation.

Figure 6. (a) MOSS-0.15 mm³ and (b) MOSS-0.24 mm³ fast neutron count rates (in blue) compared to the BME reference detector (in red).

Despite the encountered degradation, the scintillator provided signals up to 1 kW which shows promise for short irradiations. Figure 7 shows the results for all other power steps measurements with several MOSS versions. MOSS-0.24 mm³ exhibits the same count rates after multiple irradiations at 1 kW. To achieve this, for each measurement, a bespoke ROI was chosen via expert judgment. Although the replicated high-power counting performance is encouraging, a potential bias from bespoke ROIs cannot be excluded. Conversely, these results are in contradiction with the degradation statements from before. Firstly by the change of the ROI and secondly by the different type of response of the scintillator at higher fluxes.

Figure 7 (a) shows the results for multiple irradiations of the MOSS-0.15 mm³. It exhibits in a different way the divergence of the detector up to 1 kW.

In Figure 7 (b), we plotted multiple experiments with a MOSS-0.24 mm³. The CROCUS results are added for comparison. The count rate in CROCUS is lower than in BME for the same powers, a direct consequence of the vicinity of the detector to the core center of BME, whereas in CROCUS the MOSSs were set in the outer fuel zone.

At the highest reactor powers, a reduction in the measured count rate is observed, which can be attributed to the gradual decrease in neutron detection during the acquisition step. Owing to the higher noise energy observed in BME, the ROI was defined at higher energies than in CROCUS.

Figure 7. Fast neutron count rate evolutions for two MOSS detectors in comparison with the BME current chamber reference monitor, three repetitions of the experiment: MOSS-0.15 mm³ (a) and MOSS-0.24 mm³ (b). Data from CROCUS is shown in comparison for (b) as well.

To conclude, the MOSS detectors exhibit live fast neutron count rates up to 1 kW and provided a linear signal up to 300 W before starting to diverge. We hypothesize this to stem from gamma-ray pileups. A test with a bare optical fiber (i.e. without scintillator) was carried out in BME and showed no significant signal e.g. due to Cerenkov light in the fiber. This is to be confirmed in future work with simulations of the reaction rates and other developments [22], [23].

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper shows the results of high-power irradiation of a miniature organic fast neutron detector coupled to an optical fiber. First CROCUS zero-power reactor was used as reference neutron source up to 90 W reactor power. The results showed the MOSS providing a proportional fast neutron counting response to reactor power. Then, high-flux measurements up to 1 kW were performed at the BME training reactor. MOSS detectors of different sizes and different PMT systems were tested. We observed a linear counting response to about 300 W. For higher powers, a divergence from linearity was observed. The main hypothesis for the cause is pileup events not filtered by the PSD. We also observed count rate decrease at higher powers. This effect indicates a degradation of some part of the detector, yet repetitions of the same experiment yielded similar results. Tests for possible causes, such as fiber darkening or scintillator damage are necessary next steps. Further developments include a more detailed pulse shape analysis, with the goal of filtering pileups [24].

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